

FAKIRA AS A REBELLIOUS PERSONALITY

Dr. Madhav Shankar Waghmare

Assistant Professor

Department of political Science G.T. Patil College, Nandurbar.

Abstract :

The present study will focus on Fakira as a rebellious personality , Fakira is a protagonist character in Fakira novel. Fakira is one of the famous novels written by Anna Bhau Sathe. Maharashtra government has awarded a prize to novel in 1959. This novel is based on sufferings and humiliations in the course of his life. The novel narrates Fakira's life who is an outcast. A novel also depicts Fakira's fighting spirit against the British government and its injustices.

Introduction :

The beginning of Indian ancient literature is from Rigveda, Ved, which were written in Sanskrit, because Sanskrit was identified with brahminical religion of the Vedas Buddhism and Jainism Adopted other literary languages (Pali and Ardhamagadhi, respectively.) Ancient literature also seems religious literature because saints like Tukaram, Kabir, Eknath have opposed to injustice discrimination, casteism, untouchability etc.

And they justified equality, justice, humanity through their books. The same seems in the Indian medieval literature.

In the medieval period, the social problems of the lower caste, untouchables were highlighted in the writings of Rabindranath Tagore, Guru Nanak, Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi etc. Gandhi's indigo revolt was a revolt for farmers against the indigo planters, which had happened in Bengal in 1859. (Wikipedia).

The modern literature also depicts the problems in Indian society. Social reformers like Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, Mahatma Jotiba Phule, Shahu Maharaj, Anna Bhau Sathe attacked on the evil practices in Indian society. Ambedkar, according to article 15 (Dr. Ambedkar,6) prevents discrimination untouchability and evil practices through their 2 books. Time to time, in later time, Shahu Maharaj honored the Dalits by giving fifty percent reservation in Government jobs in 26th July 1902. And similarly Anna Bhau Sathe attacked on evil practices through his literature. In his *Fakira* touched to equality, justice, opportunity. In this novel, Fakira revolts against the British Raj and opposes its injustices.

Objectives of the Research Paper.

1. To focus Fakira as a rebellious personality.

2. To analyze the role of Fakira in *Fakira*.

2. Research Methodology:

This paper presents an analysis of Fakira and his role in *Fakira*. This research paper is depended on secondary data and other secondary information collected by the others various research papers, article, news papers etc. And here descriptive and analytical methods are used for completion of paper.

3. Fakira for Social Justice:

Fakira is an award-winning novel of Anna Bhau Sathé in 1961. In this novel, Sathé depicted the life of the deprived, Fakira is a protagonist character who fights against all odds in the British time because Fakira has to establish equality among people. Sathé in time of the British, the deprived people had to suffer untouchability, discrimination, inequality by upper caste people because they were exploited by upper caste people because Indian system was responsibility to this so in this novel, Fakira revolts against the British and he steals Britishers' treasury and distributes equal to people. Fakira fights against discrimination, inequality, untouchability, injustice to become by upper caste people.

Fakira doesn't suffer injustice of upper caste people, their exploitation, discrimination etc, Thus the role of Fakira as a revolter for establishing social justice is important one.

5. Fakira as a Rebellious Personality:

The novel *Fakira* depicts Fakira's fighting spirit against the British government and its injustices and The novel depicts the social reality of how historically Dalit's occupied social periphery and have been excluded from the core of society. In this novel, they were exploited, harassed and discriminated with them at large scale so Fakira fights against every bad practice of upper caste and the British for giving justice to the lower caste people.

5. Fakira as a Man of Equality:

Sathé portrays Fakira the protagonist, revolter against the rural orthodox system and British Raj to save his community from utter starvation. (en.m.wikipedia.org.) Fakira fights for the rights of the masses because in that time orthodox Indian people and the Britishers were torturing and exploiting to lower caste people for, prevention of this Fakira revolts and fights against the British and Fakira steals the treasury of Britishers and distributes equal to all people. So, at the end Fakira was killed by Britishers because he was fighting against every evil practices of orthodox Indian people and Britishers so here Fakira seems a man of equality doing good works for all people.

5. Fakira for the Deprived :

Sathe has focused the problems pangs, troubles of lower caste people and showed that how they fight and oppose for justice, equal rights against the Britishers and Indian Orthodox people and their culture. Fakira, a hero who fights for the rights of the deprived in this novel. He raises questions to caste system let alone, he steals the treasury of British and distributes equally to people.

6. Arts of Narration in Fakira :

The art of narration in A.B.Sathe's novel *Fakira* shows a skillful organization of the various tools of narration because emphasizes on point of new focus, atmosphere, characterization and imagery. The novel *Fakira* shows how the downtrodden community participated in freedom fighting movement in their own way. During the pre-independent India, the downtrodden, middle class community lived in inhuman conditions and was subjected to worst kind of humiliation, sometimes, without any cause whatsoever, Sathe has skillfully portrayed in the novel *Fakira*, downtrodden community suffered from both side, one from social discrimination and another from injustices of the British Government. Sathe's language of narration is generally plain and simple. But on occasions there are images and symbols, some of them changed with deep emotion. Indianess is also there in both speech and atmosphere. There is also poet and singer in him, it can be seen his characters. Most of Sathe's works of are is own similar thinking. The novel *Fakira* narrates failure life who is an outcaste. His suffering and number of humiliations in the course of his life occur. Thus Sathe's narrative technique is a different one as compare to others.

7. Feminism And Fakira :

Basically *Fakira* novel depicts all problems in Indian society, for example feminism, domination, patriarchy, exploitation, harassment, Suffering of the downtrodden people. *Fakira*, revolting man fights for the rights of the women and men in the British Raj and nurtures the people by giving money etc. He is the revolter of all evil practices in Indian society. Even *Fakira* fight against old culture and tradition. On the whole, Sathe in his entire novel stirred self-respect, confidence, rights of women, their role in society. Similarly *Fakira* protects the prestige of women and gives protection to all deprived people.

8. Fakira As Humanist :

Fakira is a man of equality, a great humanist who fought against old culture, tradition and British for humanism. He had to establish equality among people by annihilating this orthodox society. His revolt for humanity, equality, which is a split-giving attack to Indian orthodox society.

Conclusion:

While summing up, in the entire paper it is focused on *Fakira*'s rebellious personality And it is focused on *Fakira*'s feminism, *Fakira*'s ideology, his revolt for equal rights of the downtrodden communities. In this

paper There is also sheded light on ancient medieval, modern literature in a nut shell. On the whole paper is to focus on Fakira and his works From different perspectives.

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